

Outage performance analysis of non-orthogonal multiple access systems with RF energy harvesting

Hoang Thien Van¹, Vo Tien Anh², Danh Hong Le³, Ma Quoc Phu⁴, Hoang-Sy Nguyen⁵

^{1,2}The Saigon International University (SIU), Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

³Van Hien University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

⁴Binh Duong University, Thu Dau Mot City, Binh Duong Province, Vietnam

⁵Eastem International University, Binh Duong Province, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

Non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) has drawn enormous attention from the research community as a promising technology for future wireless communications with increasing demands of capacity and throughput. Especially, in the light of fifth-generation (5G) communication where multiple internet-of-things (IoT) devices are connected, the application of NOMA to indoor wireless networks has become more interesting to study. In view of this, we investigate the NOMA technique in energy harvesting (EH) half-duplex (HD) decode-and-forward (DF) power-splitting relaying (PSR) networks over indoor scenarios which are characterized by log-normal fading channels. The system performance of such networks is evaluated in terms of outage probability (OP) and total throughput for delay-limited transmission mode whose expressions are derived herein. In general, we can see in details how different system parameters affect such networks thanks to the results from Monte Carlo simulations. For illustrating the accuracy of our analytical results, we plot them along with the theoretical ones for comparison.

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Corresponding Author:

Danh Hong Le

Van Hien University

Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Email: danhlh@vhu.edu.vn

1. INTRODUCTION

NOMA technology is well-known because of its ability to serve multiple users exploiting the same resource block [1], [2]. Additionally, we can find in the existing literature the principal elements of NOMA, which have been well investigated, such as superposition coding, successive interference cancellation (SIC). Thus, it is needless to mention the convenience of deploying NOMA for the massive connectivity need of 5G and IoT applications, [3]-[8]. Besides, simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) systems, as the name suggests, exploit the radio frequency (RF) for EH and transferring data to power finite-capacity batteries in wireless relaying networks, [9]-[14]. Indeed, we can find a wide range of studies relating to EH relaying networks for outdoor scenarios in [15]-[24]. Specifically, in [15]-[17], the two relaying protocols namely power splitting-based (PS) and time switching-based (TS) and their hybrid version in cooperative relaying networks were studied. Additionally, two relay operation modes so-called amplify-and-forward (AF) and decode-forward (DF) were investigated in [18]. Especially in [22]-[24], the authors analyzed the system performance of SWIPT networks in the context of NOMA. On the contrary, despite being excellent in modelling the indoor fading variations caused by building walls and moving objects [25]-[27], log-normal fading channels are not studied that intensively comparing to common fading channels

such as Rayleigh, Nakagami-m. Among the rare study pieces concerning indoor log-normal fading, there were [28-31]. Motivated by the above works, in this paper, we investigate the outage performance of NOMA EH-HD-DF-PSR networks. Differing itself from the existing works, we analyze the networks in indoor scenarios which we model with log-normal fading channels. In section 2, we describe the system model. Section 3 presents the \mathcal{OP} and throughput analytical expressions of the in-studied networks. In section 4, we discuss the simulation results from the derived expressions. Finally, section 5 concludes our paper.

2. SYSTEM MODEL

Depicted in Figure 1(a) is the in-studied system model whereas a source (S) attempts to transmit data to two user devices denoted as U_1 and U_2 . However, we can see that the $S \rightarrow U_2$ communication link cannot be realized because of the in-between obstacle. Thereby, U_1 is employed to relay the data transmitted from S to U_2 . It should be noted that U_1 operates in DF mode and is energized by EH the signal that S sends. The $S \rightarrow U_1$ and $U_1 \rightarrow U_2$ distances are denoted with d_1 and d_2 , and assigned with complex channel coefficients of h_1 and h_2 , respectively. Besides, there are two random variables (RVs) denoted as $|h_1|^2$ and $|h_2|^2$. The two RVs are independently and identically distributed (i.i.d) over the time block in the log-normal distribution manner, with parameters $LN(\mu_{h_1}, \sigma_{h_1}^2)$ and $LN(\mu_{h_2}, \sigma_{h_2}^2)$, respectively. Additionally, we have μ_{h_1} is the mean value of $10 \log(|h_1|^2)$, and $\sigma_{h_i}^2$ is the standard deviation of $10 \log(|h_i|^2)$, $i \in \{1,2\}$. With regard to Figure 1(b), we can see the PSR protocol that U_1 employs in this study for EH and information transmission (IT) over the time block T . Specifically, we have T divided into two $T/2$ blocks with details below.

Figure 1. This figure are; (a) System model, (b) PSR protocol

2.1. In first time slot

During the first time slot $T/2$, S transmits data with a transmission power of E_s to U_1 . The second time slot, remaining $T/2$, is used for IT from U_1 to U_2 . As aforementioned, PSR protocol U_1 separates the E_s to two portions for EH and IT purposes. We denote the power splitting (PS) ratio as α , $0 < \alpha < 1$. Thereby, at U_1 , the energy amount from EH process is:

$$E_H = \eta\alpha|h_1|^2 d_1^{-m} E_s (T/2), \tag{1}$$

where $0 < \eta < 1$ is the EH efficiency at the energy receiver, determined by the rectifier and EH circuitry that U_1 deploys. Employing the superposition property of S's transmit signal in NOMA scheme [1, 2], the received signal at U_1 is expressed as shown in (2).

$$y_{U_1} = h_1 \left(\sqrt{a_1 E_S d_1^{-m}} x_1 + \sqrt{a_2 E_S d_1^{-m}} x_2 \right) + n_{U_1}, \quad (2)$$

where we have a_1 and a_2 are, respectively, the power allocation coefficients of target signal x_1 and x_2 that S attempts to send to U_1 and U_2 . Besides, we have the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at U_1 , which is n_{U_1} , with variance N_0 . We assume that $E[x_1^2] = E[x_2^2] = 1$. Since U_2 is further from S than U_1 , it is allocated with more power. Thus, we have $a_2 > a_1 > 0$, which satisfies $a_1 + a_2 = 1$. Additionally, the U_1 consumes a portion of the energy harvested for its operation while the rest is utilized for DF the received signal to U_2 . Thereby, we can express the transmission power at U_1 with regard to the harvested energy E_H as shown in (3).

$$E_{U_1} = \frac{E_H}{(T/2)} = \frac{\eta \alpha |h_1|^2 d_1^{-m} E_S (T/2)}{(T/2)} = \eta \alpha |h_1|^2 d_1^{-m} E_S. \quad (3)$$

Considering (2), we have the received signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) at U_1 for detecting the signal x_2 of U_2 formulated in (4).

$$\gamma_{U_1, x_2} = \frac{(1-\alpha) |h_1|^2 d_1^{-m} a_2 \delta}{(1-\alpha) |h_1|^2 d_1^{-m} a_1 \delta + 1}, \quad (4)$$

where $\delta = E_S / \sigma^2$ is the transmit signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

The U_1 receives then decodes the signal x_1 and x_2 from S with the help of SIC [23]. The received SNR that U_1 exploits to identify its signal, x_1 is formulated as (5).

$$\gamma_{U_1, x_1} = (1-\alpha) |h_1|^2 d_1^{-m} a_1 \delta. \quad (5)$$

2.2. In second time slot

After decoding signal x_2 , U_1 forwards the signal to U_2 . Hence, U_2 receives the signal of:

$$y_{U_2} = \left(\sqrt{E_{U_1} d_2^{-m}} x_2 \right) h_2 + n_{U_2}, \quad (6)$$

where n_{U_2} is denoted the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at U_2 , with variance N_0 . We substitute (3) into (6) to obtain:

$$y_{U_2} = \sqrt{\eta \alpha d_1^{-m} d_2^{-m} \delta} h_1 h_2 x_2 + n_{U_2}. \quad (7)$$

Accordingly, the received SNR at U_2 is expressed as

$$\gamma_{U_2, x_2} = |h_1|^2 |h_2|^2 d_1^{-m} d_2^{-m} \eta \alpha \delta. \quad (8)$$

3. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

3.1. Outage performance at U_1

In NOMA setup, U_1 is not subject to any outage event X on condition that both the x_1 and x_2 that it receives from S are successfully decoded. Hence, with regard to (4) and (5), we can formulate the \mathcal{OP} of U_1 as shown in (9).

$$\mathcal{OP}_{U_1, X} = 1 - \Pr(\gamma_{U_1, x_2} > \gamma_{th_2}, \gamma_{U_1, x_1} > \gamma_{th_1}), \quad (9)$$

where $\gamma_{th_1} = 2^{2R_{U_1}} - 1$ and $\gamma_{th_2} = 2^{2R_{U_2}} - 1$. To detect the x_1 and x_2 , the target rates R_{U_1} and R_{U_2} are deployed, respectively. The probability function is $Pr(\cdot)$. In general, the \mathcal{OP} of U_1 , deploying X protocol, is expressed in the Theorem 1 as (10),
Theorem 1.

$$\mathcal{OP}_{U_1, X} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left[\frac{\xi \ln(\max(\omega_1, \omega_2)) - 2\mu_{h_1}}{2\sqrt{2}\sigma_{h_1}} \right] \right), \quad (10)$$

where $\omega_1 = \frac{\gamma_{th_1}}{a_1 d_1^{-m} (1-\alpha)\delta}$ and $\omega_2 = \frac{\gamma_{th_2}}{d_1^{-m} \delta (1-\alpha) (a_2 - a_1 \gamma_{th_2})}$ with $a_2 > a_1 \gamma_{th_2}$.

Proof:

We can compute the \mathcal{OP} of U_1 from (11):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{OP}_{U_1, X} &= 1 - \Pr(|h_1|^2 \geq \max(\omega_1, \omega_2)) \\ &= \Pr(|h_1|^2 < \max(\omega_1, \omega_2)) = F_X(\max(\omega_1, \omega_2)), \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $X = |h_1|^2$. We symbolized the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the RV X as $F_X(\max(\omega_1, \omega_2))$. Because X is distributed following log-normal method, the CDF can be expressed as (12).

$$F_X(\max(\omega_1, \omega_2)) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left[\frac{\xi \ln(\max(\omega_1, \omega_2)) - 2\mu_{h_1}}{2\sqrt{2}\sigma_{h_1}} \right] \right), \quad (12)$$

where we have the error function $\operatorname{erf}[\cdot]$ as shown in (13).

$$\operatorname{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x \exp(-t^2) dt \quad (13)$$

we substitute (12) into (11) to prove the correctness of the Theorem 1. The proof ends here.

3.2. Outage performance at U_2

Additionally, U_2 experiences outage event either when U_1 fails to detect x_2 to forward to U_2 or x_2 is detected but cannot be recovered by U_2 . Thus, with regard to (4) and (8), the \mathcal{OP} of U_2 is expressed as (14).

$$\mathcal{OP}_{U_2, x_2} = \Pr(\gamma_{U_1, x_2} < \gamma_{th_2}) + \Pr(\gamma_{U_2, x_2} < \gamma_{th_2}, \gamma_{U_1, x_2} > \gamma_{th_2}). \quad (14)$$

Similarly, the \mathcal{OP} of U_2 , deploying signal x_2 protocol, as shown in (15).

Theorem 2.

$$\mathcal{OP}_{U_2, x_2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \mathcal{A} + \frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{h_1}^2}} \int_{\omega_2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} \exp \left(-\frac{(\xi \ln(x) - 2\mu_{h_1})^2}{8\sigma_{h_1}^2} \right) (1 + \mathcal{B}) dx \right), \quad (15)$$

where $\mathcal{A} = \operatorname{erfc} \left[\frac{\xi \ln(\omega_2) - 2\mu_{h_2}}{2\sqrt{2}\sigma_{h_2}} \right]$, $\mathcal{B} = \operatorname{erf} \left[\frac{\xi \ln \left(\frac{\omega_3}{x} \right) - 2\mu_{h_2}}{2\sqrt{2}\sigma_{h_2}} \right]$, and $\omega_3 = \frac{\gamma_{th_2}}{\eta\alpha\delta d_1^{-m} d_2^{-m}}$.

Proof:

From (14), we can rewrite the \mathcal{OP}_{U_2, x_2} as a sum of two probabilities as shown in (16).

$$\mathcal{OP}_{U_2, x_2} = \underbrace{\Pr\left(|h_1|^2 < \omega_2\right)}_{\mathcal{P}_1} + \underbrace{\Pr\left(|h_1|^2 > \omega_2, |h_2|^2 < \frac{\gamma_{th_2}}{\eta\alpha\delta d_1^{-m} d_2^{-m} |h_1|^2}\right)}_{\mathcal{P}_2}. \quad (16)$$

It is possible to calculate the term \mathcal{P}_1 from

$$\mathcal{P}_1 = \Pr\left(|h_1|^2 < \omega_2\right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left[\frac{\xi \ln(\omega_2) - 2\mu_{h_1}}{2\sqrt{2}\sigma_{h_1}} \right] \right). \quad (17)$$

Additionally, \mathcal{P}_2 is calculated deploying the probability density function (PDF) and CDF of the aforementioned X and $Y = |h_2|^2$ as shown in (18):

$$\mathcal{P}_2 = \int_{\omega_2}^{\infty} f_X(x) F_Y \left(\frac{\gamma_{th_2}}{\eta\alpha\delta d_1^{-m} d_2^{-m} x} \right) dx, \quad (18)$$

where

$$f_X(x) = \frac{\xi}{2x\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{h_1}^2}} \exp \left[-\frac{(\xi \ln(x) - 2\mu_{h_1})^2}{8\sigma_{h_1}^2} \right], \quad (19)$$

and

$$F_Y \left(\frac{\gamma_{th_2}}{\eta\alpha\delta d_1^{-m} d_2^{-m} x} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left[\frac{\xi \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_{th_2}}{\eta\alpha\delta d_1^{-m} d_2^{-m} x} \right) - 2\mu_{h_2}}{2\sqrt{2}\sigma_{h_2}} \right] \right). \quad (20)$$

Finally, (17) and (18) are substituted into (16) to obtain the \mathcal{OP} of U_2 , which is (15).

3.3. Total system throughput

It should be noted that for delay-limited transmission mode, the received signal is decoded by the destination node one block after another. Additionally, we have S transmit information with a constant rate of R_{U_i} , $i \in (1, 2)$, which is determined by the \mathcal{OP} over log-normal fading channels. For X protocol in the delay-limited transmission mode [21], we have the total system throughput as shown in (21).

$$\tau_X = (1 - \mathcal{OP}_{U_1, X}) R_{U_1} + (1 - \mathcal{OP}_{U_2, x_2}) R_{U_2}, \quad (21)$$

where $\mathcal{OP}_{U_1, X}$ and \mathcal{OP}_{U_2, x_2} are consecutively taken from Theorem 1 and 2. Besides, we have the target rates being R_{U_1} and R_{U_2} , which are respectively the target rates for U_1 , U_2 to detect x_1 and x_2 .

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the Monte Carlo simulation results of the derived expressions to show how the PS factor and the SNR affect the system performance in PSR NOMA scenario over log-normal fading channels. The simulation results are plotted in addition to the analytical results for comparison. For the simulations, we presume that $\eta = 1$, $m = 2$, $d_1 = d_2 = 2$ (m), $\sigma_{h_1} = \sigma_{h_2} = 4$ (dB), $\mu_{h_1} = \mu_{h_2} = 3$ (dB). Moreover, we use the power allocation coefficients of NOMA for U_1 and U_2 being $a_1 = 0.2$ and $a_2 = 0.8$, respectively. Last but not least, we set the target rates as $R_{U_1} = 2$ (bps/Hz) and $R_{U_2} = 1$ (bps/Hz). Figure 2 shows the \mathcal{OP} versus the PS factor, α . In general, we can see that the probability that the outage event happens to U_1 is significantly higher than that of U_2 .

The \mathcal{OP} raises constantly to the increase of the PS factor for U_1 . However, for U_2 , the \mathcal{OP} first decreases to its minimum value as PS factor approaches (0.45), then rises to its maximum when the PS factor grows further. Figures 3 and 4 consecutively plot the \mathcal{OP} and the throughput versus the SNR. Specifically, in Figure 3, it is obvious that the higher the SNR, the lower the O P. Besides, in Figure 4, we can observe that the throughput-SNR curve of U_1 is remarkably better than that of U_2 starting from SNR=2.5 (dB). Last but not least, we can see the impact of SNR on the \mathcal{OP} with two different data transmission rates in Figure 5. In particular, for the lower $R_{U_1} = R_{U_2} = R_{U_0}$ value, the system performs better indicated by the fact that the \mathcal{OP} -SNR curve converges quicker to the zeroth floor, which indicates 100% success in data transmission. In closing, we can see that the simulation results fit well the analytical ones showing the accuracy of our derived expressions.

Figure 2. The \mathcal{OP} performance versus the EH PS factor

Figure 3. The \mathcal{OP} performance versus the SNR

Figure 4. The throughput of two users versus the SNR

Figure 5. The \mathcal{OP} versus the SNR with two different data transmission rates

5. CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, we investigate the \mathcal{OP} and the total throughput for delay-limited transmission mode of NOMA EH-HD-DF-PSR networks over log-normal fading channels. In general, we can conclude that the SNR increase will lead to better throughput, which subsequently makes the \mathcal{OP} smaller. Furthermore, the network performs better with smaller data transmission rate and is more likely to experience outage event as the PS factor becomes higher.

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